

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Exploring the factors that influence the positive mindset of selected educators

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Abstract

This study attempted to ascertain a specific aspect of Philippine educators' mental health which is positive mindset. 198 educators volunteered to be the respondents of this study through convenience sampling. The respondents were from both private and public educational institutions and handled various academic levels which included kindergarten, elementary, high school, senior high and college. The Positive Mindset Index (PMI), which measures motivation, optimism, emotional stability, happiness, confidence, and control, was administered on the respondents. The findings revealed that the respondents were *happy, confident, in control, stable, motivated* and *optimistic*. However, when grouped according to marital status, the married respondents had significantly higher PMI scores than the single respondents. Significant low positive relationships between the respondents' PMI scores and their age and years of teaching were also established. When grouped according to educational attainment, the analysis of variance indicated a significant difference in the respondents' PMI scores.

Keywords: Educator; Happiness; Confidence; Control; Stability; Optimism; Positive Mindset

1. Introduction

It's a known fact that teaching is one of the most stressful occupations in the modern world. Long-term exposure to high levels of work-related stress can have a negative impact on a teacher's physical and mental well-being as well as their social and professional performance. In one study, 776 secondary school teachers in Malaysia had their levels of burnout assessed on three different dimensions (personal accomplishment, emotional weariness, and depersonalization). The researchers also looked at the sources of stress, signs of stress, and psychological symptoms of the teachers. According to the quantitative data analysis, the majority of the teachers exhibited burnout in relation to their personal achievements, work-related pressures, and time management; weariness was the most common symptom¹.

In a knowledge-based economy, education is one of the key foundations of sustainable development. One important issue influencing the quality of education is the mental health of teachers. One paper analyzed 116 studies that looked into the mental health status of Chinese teachers using a cross-temporal meta-analysis. The findings demonstrated that many teacher types had comparable trends in their mental health, which was usually declining, particularly in the areas of anger and psychoticism. This alarming discovery might point to a high-risk occupational stressor experienced by educators. Teachers who are mentally ill may experience occupational stress due to things like a constantly shifting legal environment, an excessive amount of non-teaching responsibilities, a strong focus on competitions, an overly centralized management structure in the classroom, and a low socioeconomic standing².

A study looked into the issues negatively affecting Filipino teachers' mental health. The study's findings showed that instructors deal with mental health issues in a variety of ways. Family and other social support, leisure, and spiritual activities have always been helpful during these trying times, and several studies have demonstrated their efficacy in managing mental health. Aside from these coping mechanisms, teachers have shown that they are adaptable enough to

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find methods that help them feel significantly better. Additionally, the study demonstrates how resilient educators are in the face of adversity. They accepted their challenges, but they also controlled and redirected their attention toward something constructive and upbeat³.

Emotions play a vital role in the lives of educators. However, emotions received relatively little emphasis in teacher education until recently. Furthermore, it's common to see teachers' emotions as the result of outside influences. To gain further insight into how teachers' emotions and emotion attitude affect their involvement, a study was carried out. The results of the structural equation modeling demonstrated that higher involvement was predicted by an implicit belief in the malleability of emotions through an increase in positive emotions and a decrease in negative emotions⁴.

Positive mindset is believed to be composed of six (6) elements namely, happiness, confidence, a sense of being in control, stability, motivation and optimism⁵.

With regards to happiness, two hundred and eighty-two Italian full-time in-service teachers participated in a particular study. The respondents were given the Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS), the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), the Physical and Mental Health Scales, and the School Children Happiness Inventory—a version tailored for teachers. The findings demonstrated that the association between dispositional happiness and teacher health is somewhat mediated by work-related happiness, while the relationship between self-esteem and teacher health is totally mediated by teacher happiness. Results validated the importance of self-worth in supporting behaviors linked to health, hence advancing mental and physical well-being. Teachers who report feeling pleased at work had greater levels of dispositional happiness and self-esteem, which have an effect on health problems⁶.

In terms of confidence, a study found that increases in professional capital, which includes knowledge and skill acquisition (human capital), involvement in networks of collaborative learning communities (social capital), and the capacity to exercise professional agency (decisional capital), are correlated with teachers' increases in confidence. The study came to the conclusion that mentorship is a crucial professional trait that can be developed through professional learning, and that teacher confidence is both a function and a fundamental component of teacher professional capital⁷.

With respect to control, three researches looked at the connection between subjective well-being throughout adulthood and felt control over growth. It turned out that When developmental goals were attained, older adults felt more content when they attributed their success to their own abilities, while younger adults felt more satisfied when they attributed their triumphs to their own efforts. Results indicate that throughout maturity, control perceptions adapt to age-related actual control potentials⁸.

Concerning stability, a study involving fifty college professors was conducted to determine the association between workplace spirituality, emotional stability, and occupational stress. Responses were gathered by structured questionnaires that employed the emotional stability, spiritual competence, and occupational stress scales. The study's variables were all found to be substantially correlated. The findings show that some personality traits, such as emotional stability and workplace spirituality, have a negative correlation with occupational stress and may therefore be useful in reducing occupational stress in college instructors⁹.

With regards to motivation, it has been demonstrated that teacher motivation is an important component that is strongly related to many other factors in education, including student motivation, educational reform, teaching methodology, and the psychological fulfillment and wellbeing of instructors. It has been determined that there are five research areas that are related to teacher motivation research: factors that influence teacher motivation; teacher motivation and teaching effectiveness; teacher motivation and student motivation; research on teacher motivation across disciplines; and tools for measuring teacher motivation¹⁰.

In terms of optimism, the idea that teachers can effectively instruct their children, that parents will support them, and that they will be able to push hard for learning is known as the teacher sense of academic optimism. This new construct is based on studies on learned optimism, school climate and culture, social capital theory, and social cognitive and self-efficacy theories. Academic success and general academic optimism have been linked at the school level. In a confirmatory factor analysis employing structural equation modeling, the analyses evaluated and bolstered the validity and reliability of the concept at the individual level with elementary school instructors¹¹.

Published studies on positive mindset among Filipino teachers were not encountered by this researcher. It is for this reason as well as the need to ascertain the mental health of Philippine educators that this study was conducted.

Specifically, this study sought to address the following research questions.

- What are the Positive Mindset Index (PMI) scores of the respondents when grouped according to:
 - Sex;
 - Marital status;
 - Type of school (private or public)?
- Are there differences between the PMI scores of the respondents when grouped according to:
 - Sex;
 - Marital status;
 - Type of school (private or public)?
- Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' PMI scores and their?
 - Age;
 - Years of teaching experience?
- Is there a significant difference in the respondents' PMI scores when grouped according to educational attainment?

2. Methodology

Through convenience sampling, 198 educators volunteered to be the respondents of this study. The educators who volunteered taught different levels including kindergarten, elementary, high school, senior high and college. With regards teaching experience, 16 respondents have been teaching for less than a year, 28 respondents have been teaching for 1-3 years, 74 respondents have been teaching for 4-6 years, 22 respondents have been teaching for 7-9 years, 25 respondents have been teaching for 10-12 years, 13 respondents have been teaching for 13-15 years, 6 respondents have been teaching for 16-18 years, 4 respondents have been teaching for 19-21 years and 10 respondents have been teaching for over 21 years. In terms of educational attainment, 83 respondents had bachelor's degrees, 89 respondents had obtained master's units, 13 respondents had finished their master's degrees and 13 had master's degrees while having obtained doctorate units. The Positive Mindset Index (PMI) was administered on the respondents. The six elements that make up the PMI are motivation, optimism, emotional stability, happiness, confidence, and control. The PMI has strong contemporaneous validity ($r = .678$) and internal reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.926$) when compared to the SF-36 psychological subscale. A sizable number of studies have employed and validated the PMI.

3. Results

The following tables present the data obtained and the statistical treatments applied.

Table 1 Scale of interpretation for the item weighted means of the PMI responses

Item weighted mean range	Item 1	Item 2	Item 3	Item 4	Item 5	Item 6
1.000 – 1.800	Very unhappy	Very unconfident	Very out of control	Very unstable	Very unmotivated	Very pessimistic
1.801 – 2.600	Unhappy	Unconfident	Out of control	Unstable	Unmotivated	Pessimistic
2.601 – 3.400	Moderately happy	Moderately confident	Moderately in control	Moderately stable	Moderately motivated	Moderately optimistic
3.401 – 4.200	Happy	Confident	In control	Stable	Motivated	Optimistic
4.201 – 5.000	Very happy	Very confident	Very in control	Very stable	Very motivated	Very optimistic

Table 2 PMI Item weighted means of male and female respondents

Item	Male N=63		Female N=135	
	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	4.111	Happy	4.081	Happy
2	4.206	Confident	3.985	Confident
3	3.952	In control	3.933	In control
4	3.746	Stable	3.763	Stable
5	4.111	Motivated	3.919	Motivated
6	4.238	Very optimistic	4.096	Optimistic

Table 3 Comparison of the PMI responses between male and female respondents

Welch's T-test computation		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	24.37	23.78
SD	3.00	2.49
SEM	0.38	0.21
N	63	135
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 1.3506 df = 103 standard error of difference = 0.435		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.1798 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals 0.59 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.28 to 1.45		

Table 4 PMI Item weighted means of the single and married respondents

Item	Single N=123		Married N=75	
	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	3.984	Happy	4.267	Very happy
2	4.008	Confident	4.133	Confident
3	3.919	In control	3.973	In control
4	3.634	Stable	3.960	Stable
5	3.878	Motivated	4.147	Motivated
6	4.081	Optimistic	4.240	Very optimistic

Table 5 Comparison of the PMI responses between single and married respondents

Welch's T-test computation		
Group	Single	Married
Mean	23.50	24.72
SD	2.84	2.20
SEM	0.26	0.25
N	123	75
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 3.3763 df = 184 standard error of difference = 0.360		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.0009 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be extremely statistically significant . Confidence interval: The mean of Single minus Married equals -1.22 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -1.93 to -0.51		

Table 6 PMI Item weighted means of the respondents from private and public schools

Item	Private School N=142		Public School N=56	
	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	4.099	Happy	4.071	Happy
2	4.063	Confident	4.036	Confident
3	3.965	In control	3.875	In control
4	3.732	Stable	3.821	Stable
5	3.979	Motivated	3.982	Motivated
6	4.169	Optimistic	4.071	Optimistic

Table 7 Comparison of the PMI responses between respondents from private and public schools

Welch's T-test computation		
Group	Private	Public
Mean	24.01	23.86
SD	2.76	2.46
SEM	0.23	0.33
N	142	56
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.3728		

df = 112 standard error of difference = 0.402
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.7100 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Private minus Public equals 0.15 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.65 to 0.95

Table 8 PMI item weighted means of all respondents combined

Item	All respondents combined N=198	
	Item weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	4.091	Happy
2	4.056	Confident
3	3.939	In control
4	3.758	Stable
5	3.980	Motivated
6	4.141	Optimistic

Table 9 The relationship between the respondents’ age and their PMI scores

Pearson r computation	
X Values $\Sigma = 6431$ Mean = 32.48 $\Sigma(X - M_x)^2 = SS_x = 14407.419$	X and Y Combined N = 198 $\Sigma(X - M_x)(Y - M_y) = 1258.359$ R Calculation $r = \Sigma((X - M_x)(Y - M_y)) / \sqrt{((SS_x)(SS_y))}$ $r = 1258.359 / \sqrt{((14407.419)(1406.753))} = 0.2795$ Meta Numerics (cross-check) r = 0.2795
Y Values $\Sigma = 4745$ Mean = 23.965 $\Sigma(Y - M_y)^2 = SS_y = 1406.753$	
The P-Value is .000067. The result is significant at $p < .05$.	

Table 10 The relationship between the respondents’ years of teaching experience and their PMI scores

Pearson r computation	
X Values $\Sigma = 750$ Mean = 3.788 $\Sigma(X - M_x)^2 = SS_x = 777.091$	X and Y Combined N = 198 $\Sigma(X - M_x)(Y - M_y) = 296.515$ R Calculation $r = \Sigma((X - M_x)(Y - M_y)) / \sqrt{((SS_x)(SS_y))}$ $r = 296.515 / \sqrt{((777.091)(1406.753))} = 0.2836$ Meta Numerics (cross-check)
Y Values $\Sigma = 4745$ Mean = 23.965	

$\sum(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1406.753$	$r = 0.2836$
The P-Value is .000051. The result is significant at $p < .05$.	

Table 11 Difference between the PMI scores according to respondents' educational attainment

Summary of Data					
	Treatments				
	Finished Bachelor's degree	Bachelor's degree with master's units	Finished master's degree	Master's degree with doctorate units	Total
N	83	89	13	13	198
$\sum X$	1919	2177	324	325	4745
Mean	23.1205	24.4607	24.9231	25	23.965
$\sum X^2$	44827	53935	8104	8253	115119
Std.Dev.	2.3654	2.7882	1.5525	3.266	2.6722
Result Details					
Source	SS	df	MS		
Between-treatments	106.9219	3	35.6406	F = 5.31937	
Within-treatments	1299.8306	194	6.7002		
Total	1406.7525	197			
The f-ratio value is 5.31937. The p-value is .001523. The result is significant at $p < .05$.					

4. Discussion

Based on Table 2, it can be observed that in 5 out of 6 items, males and females obtained the same verbal interpretations. It is only in the 6th item where males acquired a verbal interpretation of *very optimistic*.

Looking at Table 3, the Welch's t-test calculation between the male and female PMI scores revealed that there is no significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to sex.

Table 4 shows the PMI item weighted means when the respondents are grouped according to marital status. In items 2, 3, 4 and 5 both groups obtained the same verbal interpretation. However, the married respondents acquired the verbal interpretations of very happy and very optimistic in items 1 and 6, respectively.

It can be observed in Table 5, that Welch's t-test calculation between the single and married PMI scores revealed that there is an extremely significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to marital status. And because the married respondents obtained a higher mean, it can be inferred that the married respondents have a significantly higher positive mindset than single respondents.

Table 6 presents the PMI item weighted means when the respondents are grouped according to whether they teach at a private or public school. In all 6 items, both groups obtained the same verbal interpretations.

Looking at Table 7, the Welch's t-test calculation between the PMI scores of the respondents working in private and public schools revealed that there is no significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to the type of school in which they teach.

Table 8 presents the item weighted means of all the respondents combined. The verbal interpretations obtained reveal that the respondents are *happy, confident, in control, stable, motivated* and *optimistic*.

It can be observed in Table 9 that the Pearson r calculation revealed an r value of 0.2795 and with a p value of .000067, it can be inferred that there is a significant low positive relationship between the respondents' age and PMI scores.

Table 10 presents the Pearson r calculation which revealed an r value of 0.2836. And with a p value of .000051, it can be inferred that there is a significant low positive relationship between the respondents' years of teaching experience and PMI scores.

It can be seen in Table 11 that the analysis of variance calculation produced an f-ratio of 5.31937 and with a p value of .001523, it can be inferred that there is a significant difference in the PMI scores of the respondents when grouped according to educational attainment.

5. Conclusions

In general, all 198 respondents obtained PMI item weighted means that indicated that they were *happy, confident, in control, stable, motivated and optimistic*.

No significant differences were found between the respondents' PMI scores when grouped according to sex or type of school in which they taught. However, a significant difference in their PMI scores was established when grouped according to marital status and that the married respondents had significantly higher PMI scores than single respondents.

Significant low positive relationships were observed between the respondents' PMI scores and their age and years of teaching.

It was further found that there is a significant difference in the PMI scores of the respondents when grouped according to educational attainment.

Recommendations

Since the respondents in general seem to exhibit healthy PMI scores in all 6 areas, no intervention appears necessary. Based on the findings, the respondents can expect that their PMI scores could potentially increase with age and with more years of teaching experience as well as when they choose to enter into marriage.

This study is limited by the sampling method used and the size of the sample. Further research to verify the findings can be done using larger and more random samples.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express his deepest gratitude to the respondents of this study and to the author of the Positive Mindset Index (PMI).

Statement of ethical approval

The researcher declares that this study strictly adhered to the ethics of research. Freedom to withdraw at any time from the study was made known to the participants, their identities were anonymized, the participants were not exposed to any physical, psychological or social harm and the results were used for research purposes only. The researcher further ensured steps to prevent bias in the interpretation of the data. Lastly, there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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